

COMPARISON BETWEEN DIFFERENT BRAND AND MARKET SHARE OF ATORVASTATIN IN KALAMB AND YAVATMAL CITY

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Article Received on 05 May 2026,
Article Revised on 25 May 2026,
Article Published on 01 June 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20458401>

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How to cite this Article: Mr. Shreyash Deorao Katole*, Miss. Khushi Subhaschandra Kothari, Miss. Madhuri Gajanan Bhade, Associate Prof. Jitesh V. Bhojar, Dr. Rahul Bijwar Sir (2026). Comparison Between Different Brand and Market Share of Atorvastatin in Kalamb and Yavatmal City. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(11), 1619–1636.

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ABSTRACT

This project focuses on the comparison of different brands and market share of Atorvastatin in Kalamb and Yavatmal city. Atorvastatin is a widely used anti-hyperlipidemic drug prescribed for lowering cholesterol levels and preventing cardiovascular diseases. The study was conducted through face-to-face surveys with doctors and pharmacists to understand prescribing patterns, brand preference, patient awareness, and sales trends of various atorvastatin brands such as Atorva, Aztor, Storvas, Lipvas, Tonact, and Atocor. Data were collected from different medical stores in both regions over four months (January to April). The survey also evaluated the influence of marketing strategies, product availability, pricing, and doctor recommendations on market performance. The findings indicate that certain brands like Aztor and Storvas showed higher sales and market penetration in several medical stores, while customer

preference and physician prescribing habits played a major role in brand success. This study helps in understanding the competitive pharmaceutical market and the effectiveness of marketing strategies used for atorvastatin products.

KEYWORDS: Atorvastatin, statin drug, market share, pharmaceutical marketing, cardiovascular diseases, cholesterol-lowering agents.

INTRODUCTION

What is Product Survey?

A product survey is a research gathering comments and opinions from various people

regarding a product. It aims to learn how the market reacts to the product, what customer like best and what could be improved. What is product survey?

Simply put, a product survey is a tool that a company can use to learn what their users think about their products. Running a survey before launching a product means you get to see what people really want and need.^[1]

Why use surveys?

Surveys are incredibly versatile methods of research that allow you to transform feedback into data. Find out how your customers feel about your brand, measure employee engagement, or explore market segment all possible with a survey. Surveys are versatile, valuable, and vital to your market research.^[2]

Different Type of Survey Methods

Different surveys serve different purpose, which is why there are a number of them to choose from. “What are the type of surveys. I should use,” you ask? Here ‘s a look at the 17 type of survey methods researchers use today. Different type of survey method help provide different kinds of information or insights that you seek.^[3]

Types of Survey Methods

1. Interview
2. Online Survey Method
3. Intercept Survey
4. AI survey
5. Paper Survey
6. SMS Survey
7. Mobile Survey
8. QR Code Survey

1. Interviews

Also known as in-person surveys or household surveys, this used to be one of the most popular types of survey to conduct. Researchers like them because they involve getting face-to-face with individuals, this method of surveying may seem antiquated when today we have online surveying at our fingertips. However, interviews still serve a purpose.^[4]

2. Online Survey Method

Online surveys are one of the most popular types of survey methods for good reason. First, they are accessible, economical, and easy to share at the click of a button. Second, they are fast you can get responses within hours, if not minutes. Third, they come with extra features such as templates, images, skip logic, compulsory questions, or a minimum character count.^[5]

3. Intercept Surveys

While interviews tend to choose respondents and have controls in place, intercept surveys (or "man on the spot") surveys are conducted at certain locations or events. This involves having an interviewer, or multiple interviewers, scoping out an area and asking people, generally at random, for their thoughts or viewpoints on a particular topic^[6] in the \$75100 range for each survey participant are the norm.^[8]

4. AI surveys

Artificial intelligence is the latest types of survey method. Using AI, researchers allow the technology to ask survey questions. These "Chatbots" can even ask follow-up questions on the spot based on a respondent's answer. There can be drawbacks, however. If a person suspects survey questions are coming from AI, they may be less likely to respond (or may respond incorrectly to mess with the AI). Additionally, AI is not good with emotions, so asking sensitive questions in an emotionless manner could be off putting to people.^[9]

5. Paper Surveys

Many feel that paper surveys are a thing of the past. But paper surveys help to get responses from difficult-to-reach audiences. Moreover, a paper survey is the best alternative when the respondent cannot access its online version. Paper surveys in conjunction with online surveys can boost response rates.^[10]

6. SMS Text Surveys

Many people rarely using their phone to talk anymore, and ignore calls from unknown numbers. This has given rise to the SMS (Short Messaging Service) text survey. SMS surveys are delivered via text to people who have opted in to receive notifications from the sender. This means that there is usually some level of engagement, improving response rates. The one downside is that questions typically need to be short, and answers are generally 1-2 words or simply numbers (this is why many NPS surveys, gauging customer satisfaction, are often conducted via SMS text). Be careful not to send too many text surveys, as a person can

output just as easily, usually by texting STOP.^[13]

7. Mobile Surveys

Mobile traffic has now overtaken desktop computers as the most used device for accessing the internet, with more than 54% of the share. But don't fret you don't have to create an entirely new survey to reach people on their phones or tablet. Online poll makers like Survey Legend are responsible, so when you create a desktop version of a survey, it automatically become mobile friendly. The survey renders, or displays, on any device or screen regardless of size, with elements on the page automatically rearranging themselves, shrinking or expanding as necessary.^[14]

8. QR Code Surveys

QR Code or QRC is an abbreviation of "Quick Response Code" These two-dimensional encoded images, when scanned, deliver hidden information that's stored on it. They're different from barcodes because they can house a lot more information, including website URLs, phone numbers, or up to 4,000 characters of text. The recent QR code comeback provides a good opportunity for researchers to collect data. Place the QR code anywhere on flyers, posters, billboards, commercials and all someone had to do is scan it with the mobile device to have immediate access to a survey.^[17]

DRUG PROFILE

Structure of Atorvastatin.

Drug Name:- Atorvastatin.

Drug Class:-Statin (HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor).

Category:- Anti-hyperlipidemic drug.

IUPAC Name:-(3R,5R)-7-[2-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-phenyl-4-(phenylcarbamoyl)-5-propan-2-ylpyrrol-1-yl]-3,5-dihydroxyheptanoic acid.

Molecular Formula:- C₃₃H₃₅FN₂O₅.

Molecular Weight:- 558.64 gm/mol.

Main Use:- High cholesterol, prevention of heart attack and stroke.

Rout of Administration:- Oral Administration.

Available Strengths:- 10 mg, 20 mg, 40 mg.

Dose:- Usually 10-80 mg once daily.

Absorption:- Rapidly absorbed after oral administration.

Metabolism:- Metabolized in liver by CYP3A4 enzyme.

Half-Lif :- Above 14 hours.

Excretion:- Mainly through bile.

Side effect:- Headache, muscle pain, nausea, Liver damage, etc.

Storage Condition:- Store at room temperature.

METHODOLOGY

QUESTIONERIES TO DOCTOR

- There is any alternative medications?
- There are any changes to make to diet?
- There are any habit I should avoid or adopt to improve condition?
- What could be possible side effects?
- This is drug habitual?
- Which brand drug do you prescribe for Atorvastatin?
- What dosage of Atorvastatin is being prescribed, how frequently should the patient take it?
- What information should be provided to patients regarding Atorvastatin use including proper administration?
- It can be prescribed to pregnant woman?

QUESTIONERIES TO PHARMACIST

1. What is Atorvastatin prescribed for?
2. There is any cheaper alternative?
3. Which brand of Atorvastatin does doctor prescribe most?
4. Which doctor frequently prescribe Atorvastatin?
5. Has any pharmaceutical company offered any special scheme on it to sell?
6. How do you ensure that Atorvastatin are sourced from reputable manufacturers and meet quality standards?

7. Do you accept returns or exchanges for Atorvastatin if patient change his/her mind or if there's an issue with the product?

GRAPHICAL PRESENTATION

JEEVAN MEDICAL

- In this medical four brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Atorva 20mg, Storvas 40mg, Aztor 10mg, Lipvas 20mg.
- Atorva 20mg is denoted by Purple colour line, Storvas 40mg is denoted by Orange colour line, Aztor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line and Lipvas 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Atorva in January is 20, in February is 10, in March is 35, and in April is 25.
- The unit selling in strip of Storvas in January is 25, in February is 40, in March is 20, and in April is 30.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztorin in January is 35, in February is 15, in March is 10, and in April is 35.
- The unit selling in strip of Lipvas in January is 20, in February is 35, in March is 30, and in April is 25.

BORA MEDICAL

- In this medical four brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Tonact 20mg, Storvas 40mg, Aztor 10mg, Lipvas, 20mg.
- Tonact 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Storvas 40mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Aztor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line and Lipvas 20mg is denoted by Purple colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Tonact in January is 20, in February is 25, in March is 55, and in April is 45.
- The unit selling in strip of Storvas in January is 15, in February is 25, in March is 35, and in April is 45.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 10, in February is 15, in March is 10, and in April is 25.
- The unit selling in strip of Lipvas in January is 20, in February is 25, in March is 25, and in April is 30.

SHREEJI MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Atorva 20mg, Lipvas 20mg, Aztor 10mg.
- Atorva 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Lipvas 20mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Aztor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Atorva in January is 40, in February is 35, in March is 20, and in April is 35.
- The unit selling in strip of Lipvas in January is 15, in February is 35, in March is 35, and in April is 25.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 15, in February is 15, in March is 25, and in April is 35.

SHREE DATTA MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Lipvas 20mg, Aztor 10mg, Storvas 40 mg, and Atorva 20 mg.
- Lipvas 20mg is denoted by Purple colour line, Aztor 10 mg is denoted by Orange colour line, Storvas 40 mg is denoted by Green colour line, Aztor 10mg is denoted by Blue colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Atorva in January is 25, in February is 10, in March is 8, and in April is 12.
- The unit selling in strip of Lipvas in January is 10, in February is 16, in March is 20, and in April is 15.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 20, in February is 25, in March is 15, and in April is 20.

- The unit selling in strip of Storvas in January is 15, in February is 20, in March is 15, and in April is 10.

ZAPATE MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Lipvas 20mg, Aztor 10mg, Storvas 40 mg, and Atorva 20 mg.
- Lipvas 20mg is denoted by Purple colour line, Aztor 10 mg is denoted by Orange colour line, Storvas 40 mg is denoted by Green colour line, Aztor 10mg is denoted by Blue colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Atorva in January is 20, in February is 10, in March is 15, and in April is 5.
- The unit selling in strip of Lipvas in January is 15, in February is 20, in March is 10, and in April is 10.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 45, in February is 30, in March is 35, and in April is 20.
- The unit selling in strip of Storvas in January is 20, in February is 15, in March is 20, and in April is 25.

NARESH MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Lipvas 20mg, Aztor 10mg, Storvas 40 mg, and Atorva 20 mg.
- Lipvas 20mg is denoted by Purple colour line, Aztor 10 mg is denoted by Orange colour line, Storvas 40 mg is denoted by Green colour line, Aztor 10mg is denoted by Blue colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Atorva in January is 8, in February is 10, in March is 15, and in April is 8.
- The unit selling in strip of Lipvas in January is 20, in February is 25, in March is 20, and in April is 10.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 10, in February is 15, in March is 10, and in April is 12.
- The unit selling in strip of Storvas in January is 20, in February is 15, in March is 25, and in April is 30.

LUNAWAT MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Lipvas 20mg, Aztor 10mg, Storvas 40 mg, and Atorva 20 mg.
- Lipvas 20mg is denoted by Purple colour line, Aztor 10 mg is denoted by Orange colour line, Storvas 40 mg is denoted by Green colour line, Aztor 10mg is denoted by Blue colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Atorva in January is 4, in February is 5, in March is 8, and in April is 4.
- The unit selling in strip of Lipvas in January is 2, in February is 3, in March is 4, and in April is 2.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 6, in February is 5, in March is 8, and in April is 5.
- The unit selling in strip of Storvas in January is 3, in February is 2, in March is 3, and in April is 5.

KOTHARI MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor20mg, storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20mg is denoted by blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 8, in February is 10, in March is 12, and in April is 6.

- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 8, in February is 6, in March is 10, and in April is 8.
- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 6, in February is 8, in March is 8, and in April is 10.

ANAND MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor 20mg, storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20 mg is denoted by blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 8, in February is 7, in March is 10, and in April is 8.
- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 10, in February is 11, in March is 15, and in April is 8.
- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 5, in February is 7, in March is 10, and in April is 12.

Akashay Medical

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor 20mg, storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 5, in February is 7, in March is 9, and in April is 8.
- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 10, in February is 12, in March is 8, and in April is 10.
- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 5, in February is 8, in March is 6, and in April is 8.

CHINTAMANI MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor 20mg, storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Brown colourline, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 10, in February is 10, in March is 12, and in April is 14.
- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 6, in February is 8, in March is 10, and in April is 8.
- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 8, in February is 6, in March is 10, and in April is 6.

BHAGWATI MEDICAL

- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor 20mg, storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 8, in February is 10, in March is 6, and in April is 8.
- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 6, in February is 10, in March is 8, and in April is 6.
- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 10, in February is 15, in March is 8, and in April is 5.

SAMRUDDHI MEDICAL

- This graph is of Samruddhi Medical Store Kalamb
- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor 20mg, storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 15, in February is 12, in March is 14, and in April is 10.
- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 10, in February is 12, in March is 8, and in April is 12.
- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 8, in February is 10, in March is 6, and in April is 8.

EKANTH MEDICAL

- This graph is of Ekant Medical Store Kalamb
- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor 20mg, storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Brown colour line, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 10, in February is 8, in March is 12 , and in April is 10.
- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 15, in February is 12, in March is 8, and in April is 12.
- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 6, in February is 5, in March is 10, and in April is 15.

VIDARBHA MEDICAL

- This graph is of Vidarbha Medical Store Kalamb
- In this medical three brand are available of drug Atorvastatin are Aztor 20mg, Storvas 10mg, Atocor 10mg.
- Aztor 20mg is denoted by Blue colour line, Storvas 10mg is denoted by Orange colour line, Atocor 10mg is denoted by Green colour line.
- The unit selling in strip of Aztor in January is 15, in February is 10, in March is 12 , and in April is 8 .
- The unit selling in strip of storvas in January is 10, in February is 8, in March is 8, and in

April is 10.

- The unit selling in strip of Atocor in January is 8, in February is 5, in March is 5, and in April is 10.

PIE CHART

- Aztor (10mg/20mg) leads the market with a 28.7% share (depicted by the Dark Green Colour segment).
- Storvas (10mg/20mg) follows closely with 26.6% (shown in Purple Colour).
- Lipvas (20mg) captures 17.9% of the market (represented in Blue Colour).
- Atorva (20mg) captures 13.3% of the market (represent in Orange Colour).
- Atocor (10mg) captures 8.8% of the market (represent in Violet Colour).
- Tonact (20mg) has the lowest share at 5.0% of the market (represent in Light Green Colour).

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that Atorvastatin is one of the most commonly prescribed statin drugs for the management of high cholesterol and prevention of cardiovascular diseases in Kalamb and Yavatmal regions. Different brands of atorvastatin showed variation in sales and market share depending on factors such as doctor preference, product availability, pricing, promotional activities, and patient trust. Among the surveyed brands, Aztor, Storvas, and Atorva demonstrated better market performance in many medical stores. The survey also revealed that healthcare professionals prefer brands that provide good therapeutic outcomes, affordability, and easy availability. Effective pharmaceutical marketing and strong doctor–

pharmacist relationships significantly influence prescribing and selling patterns. Overall, the study highlights the importance of market analysis in understanding consumer behavior, brand competition, and the role of marketing strategies in the pharmaceutical industry.

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